

MHD STAGNATION POINT FLOW INTO A POROUS MEDIA THAT STRETCHING OR SHRINKING

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ABSTRACT

The numerical investigation focuses on the two-dimensional magnetohydrodynamic stagnation point flow over a surface that is either stretching or shrinking. The surface velocity is considered to follow a linear mass flow. The flow and thermal fields are analyzed with respect to key governing parameters, including the magnetic parameter K , the fluid temperature index m , the stretching/shrinking parameter λ , and the suction/injection parameters. Through the application of a suitable similarity transformation, the boundary layer partial differential equations are simplified into a set of nonlinear ordinary differential equations (ODEs). These equations are then numerically solved using MATLAB's built-in boundary value problem solver, BVP4C. Graphical representations of the flow and heat transfer characteristics enable the analysis of different values of the governing factors. The results show that the magnetic parameter increases the temperature gradient, while both the thermal conductivity parameter and magnetic flux contribute to a reduction in flow velocity. Within a certain range of λ , two solutions are possible. For the stretching case ($\lambda > 0$), only one solution exists, whereas for the shrinking case ($\lambda < 0$), two distinct solutions are found.

Keywords: stagnation-point flow; porous medium; stretching/shrinking sheet; heat generation.

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1. Introduction

Recent studies have extensively explored the movement of viscous fluids near the stagnation zones of solid surfaces. A stagnation point occurs when the flow of fluid is obstructed by a solid boundary. Stagnation point flows have numerous practical applications, including phase change cooling, rust-resistant bearing designs, high-velocity flow analysis, and calculating heat and mass transfer rates in the stagnation regions of structures. Additionally, these flows are critical in processes like wire drawing, polymer extrusion, cooling of nuclear reactors, and cooling of electronic devices. In 1911, [1] conducted the first analysis of stagnation point flow, offering an exact solution for two-dimensional stagnation point flow over a stationary surface.

Since that time, many researchers, such as [2], [3], and [4], have continued to investigate this field. A recent study by [5] focused on the influence of stratification and cross-diffusion on magneto-convective stagnation point flow within porous media. The result suggests that the thermal stratification parameter contributes to an increased heat transfer rate at the stagnation point. Meanwhile, [3] found that in the flow of both single-walled carbon nano tubes, adjusting the nano particle volume fraction and controlling the magnetic parameter can reduce skin friction.

Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) has attracted a lot of interest from scientists since it may make it impossible to alter fluid flow or heat transfer characteristics. When a fluid flow animated by a well-built attractive field produces Lorentz forces, this phenomenon happens (see [6]). The continuous MHD flow past a stretched surface was the initial focus of this investigation, which was started by [7]. The usefulness of MHD in postponing the boundary layer's separation is examined by other scholars from various angles by [8, 9], and 10. It is true that the magnetic value may delay the perimeter layer's separation from the diminishing exterior, as shown in the work of [9].

A few academics, including [12] and [13], have examined shrinking sheets in the literature, nevertheless. The suction effect of a shrinking sheet has been studied recently by [11]. To fill this void and expand upon the findings of [11], the present study focusses on the problem of MHD standstill point flow towards a shrinking sheet in a porous medium. We will use MATLAB's BVP4C boundary value problem solver to determine which of the two solutions is stable by doing a stability evaluation.

2. Fundamental Equations

The flow of a viscous and incompressible fluid with a constant maximum hydrodynamic drag (MHD) in two dimensions, across a permeable stretching/shrinking surface, is examined. The fluid has a velocity $U_w(x)$. In the case of stretching, the parameter λ is more than 0, and in the case of shrinking, it is less than zero (see Fig. 1), with x being a measured coordinate along the stretch/shrink surface. The flow can only be up to $y > 0$, as y is the normal to the surface. We also assume that $U_e(x)$ is the free stream velocity and V_w is the mass transfer velocity. Keep in mind that T_∞ is the temperature of the surrounding fluid.

The variable in equations(2.1)-(2.4) are dimensionless.

Continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial \bar{y}} = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

Momentum equation

$$\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{y}} = \bar{U} \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}}{\partial \bar{y}^2} + \frac{\nu}{k_1} (\bar{u}_e - \bar{u}) \quad (2.2)$$

Energy equation

$$\bar{u} \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \bar{v} \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial \bar{y}} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 \bar{T}}{\partial \bar{y}^2} + \frac{Q}{\rho c_p} (T - \bar{T}_\infty) \quad (2.3)$$

with boundary conditions

$$\bar{v} = V_w, \bar{u} = \bar{u}_w, \bar{T} = \bar{T}_w = \bar{T}_\infty + T_0 e^{\frac{x}{2L}} \text{ at } \bar{y} = 0,$$

$$\bar{u} \rightarrow \bar{u}_w \bar{x}, \bar{T} \rightarrow \bar{T}_\infty, \text{ as } \bar{y} \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.4)$$

In this context $\bar{u}$ and $\bar{v}$ represent the velocity components along the $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$ axes, respectively. T stands for the fluid temperature, α is the thermal diffusivity, ν is the kinematic viscosity, B_0 represents constant applied magnetic field, σ refers to the electrical conductivity, ρ is the fluid density, and $a, \nu,$ and m are constants. The variables are presented without their corresponding units.

$$v = \sqrt{2\nu L a} f(\eta) e^{\frac{x}{2L}}, \eta = y \sqrt{\frac{a}{2\nu L}} e^{\frac{x}{2L}}, \phi(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, u = a f'(\eta) e^{\frac{x}{2L}}$$

$$v_w = -\sqrt{\frac{\nu a}{2L}} (n f'(\eta) + f(\eta)) e^{\frac{x}{2L}} \quad (2.5)$$

$$v = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, u = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \quad (2.6)$$

The variable in equations (2.1)–(2.3) are dimensionless. Based on these assumptions, the equation that governs the flow in a constant transverse magnetic field at the boundary layer is as follows: $\bar{u}$ and $\bar{v}$ are components of the velocity along the $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$ axes, σ is the electrical conductivity, and ρ is the density. Additionally, $a, \nu,$ and m are constants. T stands for the temperature of the fluid. Now we may provide the dimensionality-free variables.

Dimensionless is the result of the variables in equations (2.1)–(2.3)

$$f''' + f f''(\eta) + 2 - 2f'^2(\eta) + 2K(1 - f') = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{1}{Pr} \theta'' + f \theta'(\eta) - f' \theta(\eta) + Q \theta = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

There exists a stream function $\psi(x, y)$ from the continuity equation (2.6) such that

$$v = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, u = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \quad (2.9)$$

This is equivalently satisfying eq (2.6). Entering (2.7) and (2.8) as substitutes for (2.9) yields

$$K = \frac{\nu L}{K_1 a e^{\frac{x}{2L}}}, Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}$$

And

$$f(0) = s, f'(0) = \lambda, \theta(0) = 1$$

$$f'(\eta) \rightarrow 1, \theta(\eta) \rightarrow 1 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty$$

Subscripts indicate partial derivatives here.

$$(i). C_f = x, Nu_x = 0, C_f = \frac{\tau_w}{\rho U_e^2}, Nu_x = \frac{q_w}{(T_w - T_\infty)} \quad (2.10)$$

To be precise, the wall shear stress (T_w) and the local heat flow (Q_w) are defined as

$$T_w = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, q_w = - \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} \quad (2.11)$$

where μ stands for dynamic viscosity. We get by substituting (2.5) into equations (2.10) and (2.11)

$$C_f = \frac{f''(0)}{2Re^{1/2}}, Nu_x = - \frac{Re^{1/2}}{2} \theta'(0) \quad (2.12)$$

where $Re = \frac{UL}{\nu}$ is the Reynolds number.

3. Findings and Analysis

This section will address how the behavior of various physical quantities, such as K, S, Pr, Q and λ , correspond to different physical parameters. With MATLAB software, the governing equations (2.7) and (2.8) with (2.9) as boundary conditions are numerically solved. Next, the numerical findings are cross-referenced with other published results to ensure their validity. We add up all the differences in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of $f''(0)$ and $\theta'(0)$ for various values of λ with $S = Q = 0$. With $Pr = 6.2$

λ	Nasir et al [11]		Present results	
-0.5	2.1882	0.6870	2.11817	0.68700
0	1.6872	1.7148	1.68722	1.71477
0.5	0.9604	2.4874	0.96042	2.487422

Display the outcomes That group, Nasir et al.[11] A solution, a solution, a solution, a solution, a solution, a first, a second, a first, a second According to the results, two different options exist for shrinking sheet.

Figure 2 shows the skin friction coefficient $f''(0)$ as a function of λ for different parameter K values. We can see from the figure that the solution exists up to the crucial value of λ_c . There is a unique solution for stretching parameters greater than zero, where λ_c is the critical value of λ , and a dual solution for shrinking surfaces, where $\lambda_c < \lambda < 0$. For certain values of λ at $M = 1$, $m = 1$, and $S = 2.5$, the lowest eigenvalue is γ . λ Initial approach A different approach $-(-2.07065, 1.49525)$ $(-2.18130, 1.62321)$ $(-2.23650, 1.70095)$

With $Pr=1$, $K=0$, and $S=1$, Figure 3 shows the graphic result of the skin friction coefficient $f''(0)$ for various values of the heat generating parameter Q . found that for varying values of Q , the skin friction sits on the same graph. What this means is that the skin friction parameter is unaffected by the heat generating parameter.

Displayed in Figure 4 is the effect of parameter K on the surface heat transfer rate. If we raise K, we can see that the local Nusselt number $f'(0)$ grows. Figure 5 shows the local Nusselt number for $Q=0,0.5$ at $Pr = 1$, $K=0$, and $S = 1$. They discovered that the rate of heat transfer reduces with increasing heat production, regardless of whether the suction parameter is present or not. Warming the fluid up is what happens when you crank up the heat generation parameter. Figure 6 displays the velocity profile of the decreasing sheet for various values of K. For both the first and second solutions, the velocity profile grows as K rises.

Figure 7 shows the temperature curve for various K values when $\lambda = -1.6$. It is evident that when the parameter K increases, the temperature profile for both solutions rise. Figure 8 demonstrates that the trend towards the velocity profile remains same for both the first and second solutions when the parameter Q is varied. On the other hand, the profile suggests that the issue could have two possible resolutions. As seen in Figure 9, the temperature profile for both the first and second solutions exhibits a pattern of rise in tandem with the parameter Q.

Figure 2. Variation of the skin friction coefficient $f''(0)$ of $K = 0, 0.1, 0.15$ when $Pr = 2$, $Q = 1$ and $S = 1$.

Figure 3. Skin friction coefficient $f''(0)$ of $Q = 0, 0.5, 1$ at $Pr = 1$, $K = 0$ and $S = 1$.

Figure 4. Local Nusselt number $-\theta'(0)$ of $K = 0, 0.1, 0.15$ at $Pr = 2, Q = 1$ and $S = 1$.

Figure 5. Local Nusselt number $-\theta'(0)$ of $Q = 0, 0.5, 1$ at $Pr = 1, K = 0$ and $S = 1$.

Figure 6. Velocity profiles of $K = 0, 0.1, 0.15$ for $\lambda = -1.6$.

Figure 7. Temperature profiles of $K = 0, 0.1, 0.15$ for $\lambda = -1.6$.

Figure 8. Velocity profiles of $Q = 0, 0.2, 1$ for $\lambda = -1$.

Figure 9. Temperature profiles of $Q = 0, 0.2, 1$ for $\lambda = -1$.

4. Conclusions

This study explored the theoretical impact of the magnetic field and temperature index parameter on fluid flow and heat transfer properties in magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) stagnation point flow near a stretching or shrinking surface, it was found that two solutions can coexist. Stability analysis reveals that only the first solution is

physically feasible. Increases in the temperature index, magnetic parameter, and suction intensity are directly linked to an enhancement in both the skin friction coefficient and heat transfer rate. As a result, flow separation from the surface can be prevented by manipulating the temperature index, suction, and magnetic effects.

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